

D2.2 - PROJECT WEBSITE

WP2

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Approved by Coordinator on: 26/04/2023

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This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

¹ PU = Public
SEN = Sensitive

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GLOSSARY / LIST OF ACRONYMS

Useful definitions of the terminology included in this deliverable that will allow the reader to better understand the scope of it:

Deliverable: report to be submitted to the European Commission compiling a description of the activities carried out in a specific work package.

Work Package: package tasks in which a project is structured.

Social Networks: websites and apps that allow users and organizations to connect, communicate, share information and form relationships. They are used in the framework of the European projects to increase the awareness of the project and the impact of the dissemination and communication activities carried out in the projects.

Stakeholders: a wide variety of people impacted or invested in the Project. The most important stakeholders in healthcare are the patients, providers (professionals) and policymakers, the three 'Ps'. Above all the patients are the most important stakeholders in healthcare

Affiliated entity: entities that have a legal link with the beneficiary of an European project and have been involved in the project to carry out specific tasks. The affiliated entities are also members of the consortium.

Partner: beneficiary of a European project. A consortium is built by several partners.

Consortium: group of entities which join their expertise and effort to carry out a project. Those entities will be the partners of the consortium and may be private or public entities.

Logo: visual identity of the project.

Typography: style or appearance of text.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Overview of the purpose of this deliverable:

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide information on how the project website has been developed and to explain why the elaboration of the website at the beginning of the project is so important to increase the impact of the project.

The project website has been developed by CSPA-SESPA-FICYT in the framework of Task 2.2 (WP2) at month 1, and the link is:

<https://c4djointaction.eu/>

The information included on the website is structured in the following areas:

- Description of the project
- List of partners
- List and description of the work packages of the project
- Description of the deliverables
- News
- Events
- Section to contact the project coordinator
- Links to the social networks: Twitter and LinkedIn
- EU funding visibility
- A new section for “Dissemination Materials” will be created to store the visual identity of the project and videos developed during the execution of the project. One folder will be created per country participant in order that they are able to upload the videos and materials created on their own language for national/regional/local dissemination purposes.

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Objectives of the development of the website:

The information of the website and social networks will be used for the promotion of the project and to foster networking and information sharing with other relevant entities, and it offers open access to all the interested persons and entities.

The overall technical objective of the task for the development of the website is to create a modern and user-friendly website by following the latest online standards in web development.

Intended audience of the deliverable and the website:

The information provided by the website will be addressed to the European Commission, the partners and affiliated entities of the project, other National and Regional health authorities from the EU Member States and beyond, all stakeholders identified in Task 2.1, Communication and Dissemination Strategy, as relevant for the project, health professionals, citizens suffering from Diabetes type 2 and the general public.

Methodology:

The methodology used for the elaboration of the website followed three steps:

- 1) Design of the logo of the project
- 2) Development of the social networks
- 3) Development of the website

The reasoning for these three steps is that for the elaboration of the website it is essential to define first the visual identity of the project. This way the dominant colours and type of letters will be selected and included in the social networks and website.

Findings, conclusions and main recommendations:

The main result of the activities concerning this deliverable is the **development of the website at month 1 of the project**. In line with this result are other two important tools created: the **logo**

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of the project and the social networks (Twitter and LinkedIn). Also, guidelines and a monitoring procedure have been developed in order to collect and spread information about the project as efficiently as possible.

The most important conclusion is that it is essential to develop the visual identity of the project, the website and social networks at the very beginning of the project to ensure the highest impact on the dissemination and communication activities.

The main recommendation for other entities developing the same activity is that the visual identity of the project, the website and the social networks should be developed as early as possible, and that the dissemination and communication strategy should be elaborated in parallel and fully aligned with them.

1. PURPOSE AND OBJECTIVES

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide information on how the project website has been created and to explain why the elaboration of the website at the beginning of the project is so important to increase the impact of the project.

The project website has been created by the coordination team at month 1 and the link is:

<https://c4djointaction.eu/>

It was considered of special interest in terms of impact to have it ready at month 1 because the kick-off meeting of the project was held on 16 & 17 February 2023. This allowed to align the launch of the website with the dissemination information on the kick-off meeting shared throughout the media (a press article was published and a piece of news appeared on TV) and the social networks.

The website has been developed in the framework of Task 2.2 and will be a platform to promote information sharing, collaboration, and networking at EU and international level. The information provided by the website will be addressed to the European Commission, the partners and affiliated entities of the project, other National and Regional health authorities from the EU

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Member States and beyond, all stakeholders identified in Task 2.1, Communication and Dissemination Strategy, as relevant for the project, health professionals, citizens suffering from Diabetes type 2, and the general public.

The information included on the website is structured in the following areas:

- Description of the project
- List of partners
- List and description of the work packages of the project
- Description of the deliverables
- News
- Events
- Section to contact the project coordinator and partners
- Links to the social networks: Twitter and LinkedIn
- EU funding visibility
- A new section will be created to store the visual identity of the project and videos developed during the execution of the project.

The information of the website and social networks will be used for the promotion of the project and to foster networking and information sharing with other relevant entities, and it offers open access to all the interested persons and institutions.

The overall technical objective of this task is to create a modern and user-friendly website by following the latest online standards in web development.

The specific objectives for the creation of the website of the project are:

- Create a high level of user-friendliness and user experience on the website;
- Develop a clean and appealing visual identity based on the existing style guide;
- Provide an intuitive to navigate website for all users available for the most popular Internet browsers;
- Develop functionalities which are crucial for a successful outcome of the project, yet at the same time do not overload the web system with unnecessary modules and functions;
- Guarantee a safe web environment in which user data will be safely stored in the database and protected from any third-party to access;

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- Encourage networking thanks to web-tools accessible online for off-line meetings, etc.;
- Contribute to knowledge sharing by achieving effective access and re-use of project outputs, publications, etc.;
- Administrate, monitor and manage registered users on the platforms;
- The project website contains detailed information on the objectives, consortium, work processes, news and the current state of the CARE4DIABETES project.
- It provides information for all interested parties and the general public.
- The website will host the outreach related content as: a periodical newsletter that provides updates on the project state and further information related to the project, dissemination material, deliverables and event calendars.
- The website also provides the links to the social media accounts (Twitter and LinkedIn).

2. METHODOLOGY

The methodology used for the elaboration of the website followed three steps:

- 1) Design of the logo of the project
- 2) Development of the social networks
- 3) Development of the website

The rationale for the selection of this methodology is that for the elaboration of the website it is essential to define first the visual identity of the project. This way the dominant colours and type of letters will be selected and included in the social networks and website. This methodology has been selected to align the development of the website with the achievement of a high impact on the dissemination activities of the project, since the audience will be able to correlate the visual identity of the project with the project on every news that appear out of the website or the social networks of the project.

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2.1. LOGO

The visual identity of the project was created during the first week of the project by CSPA-SESPA-FICYT. The coordination team planned to have it ready at the very beginning of the project since the logo would be the starting point for the development of the website and the social networks.

A Basic Manual was elaborated (see Annex I, in Spanish) which includes different versions of the logo to be used under different contexts and the corporate colors and typographies:

Positive logo, colour and black and white version:

Logo in negative, on corporate colours and other shades:

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Logos on different photographic backgrounds

Positive logo, horizontal version. Colour and black and white

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Logo in negative, horizontal version. About corporate colours and other shades:

Logos horizontal version, on different photographic backgrounds:

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Other versions:

Corporate colors (spot colours, four-colour process, RGB, HEX/HTML, RAL):

Tintas planas

Cuatricromía

RGB

HEX/HTML

RAL

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Typographies:

MUSEO SANS ROUNDED

Museo Sans Rounded 300
 abcdefghijklmñ
 opqrstuvwxyz
 ABCDEFGHIJKMNÑ
 OPQRSTUVWXYZ
 1234567890

Museo Sans Rounded 500
 abcdefghijklmñ
 opqrstuvwxyz
 ABCDEFGHIJKMNÑ
 OPQRSTUVWXYZ
 1234567890

Museo Sans Rounded 900
 abcdefghijklmñ
 opqrstuvwxyz
 ABCDEFGHIJKMNÑ
 OPQRSTUVWXYZ
 1234567890

Museo Sans Rounded 1000
 abcdefghijklmñ
 opqrstuvwxyz
 ABCDEFGHIJKMNÑ
 OPQRSTUVWXYZ
 1234567890

Snickles

*abcdefghijklmnop
 opqrstuvwxyz
 ABCDEFGHIJKMN
 OPQRSTUVWXYZ
 1234567890*

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2.2. SOCIAL NETWORKS

The social networks of the project have been developed as committed in Annex I of the Grant Agreement:

- Twitter: <https://twitter.com/C4DJointAction>
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/care4diabetes/>

Twitter:

The screenshot shows the Twitter profile for C4DJointAction. The profile picture features silhouettes of people jumping against a sunset background with the C4D logo. The bio states: "This project is cofinanced by the European Commission in the framework of the EU4 Health Programme (EU4H)". The location is Oviedo and the website is c4djointaction.eu. The profile has 45 followers and 21 following. A pinned tweet from March 16th mentions a researcher position in the project and a deadline for applications until March 25th. The right sidebar shows suggested accounts and trending topics.

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LinkedIn:

Both social network accounts have been developed by CSPA-SESPA-FICYT during the first month of the project. The logo of the project and the EU co-funding logo are included in the front screen.

Both were ready at the time of the kick-off meeting of the project to be able to promote the event, the project website and the project. A tweet per session was posted during the kick-off meeting and the hashtags of the European Commission provided by the Project Officer were used on this purpose: #EU4Health, #HealthUnion. Also the hashtags of the kick-off and the project were used: @C4DJointAction; #kickoffC4D.

The management and indicators for both social networks will be defined in the dissemination and communication strategy that is under development in the framework of Taks 2.1, but at least one post per week will be assured during the whole duration of the project.

2.3. WEBSITE

The structure of the website is divided in the following sections and specific partners are involved per website sections (related to the management of specific work-packages).

Table 1 – Website structure

Sections	Content description	In charge	Quality check	Provide input
“Home”	Welcome page	FICYT	CSPA-SESPA-FICYT	
“About”	Project summary Background Relevance Methodology	FICYT	1ST YPE ATTICA CSPA-SESPA-FICYT	Annex I of the Grant Agreement
“Partners”	List of partners	FICYT	All partners and affiliated entities	All partners and affiliated entities
“Work Packages”	List and description of work packages	FICYT	1ST YPE ATTICA CSPA-SESPA-FICYT	Annex I of the Grant Agreement
“Deliverables”	List of deliverables Reports	Partners responsible for each specific deliverable	CSPA-SESPA-FICYT	Partners responsible for each specific deliverable
“News”	News related to the activities carried out during the project	1ST YPE ATTICA CSPA-SESPA-FICYT	1ST YPE ATTICA CSPA-SESPA-FICYT	All the partners and affiliated entities
“Events”	Events organized by the consortium during the project	All partners and affiliated entities	1ST YPE ATTICA CSPA-SESPA-FICYT	All the partners and affiliated entities

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“Contact us”	Contact persons and e-mail address	FICYT	CSPA-SESPA-FICYT	CSPA-SESPA-FICYT
“EU funding visibility”	Logo, funding statement and disclaimer	CSPA-SESPA-FICYT	CSPA-SESPA-FICYT	Grant Agreement and Project Officer
“Social networks links”	Twitter LinkedIN	FICYT	1ST YPE ATTICA CSPA-SESPA-FICYT	All the partners and affiliated entities

PROJECT WEBSITE CONTENT (SCREENSHOTS)

“Home” section

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“About” section

OUR PROJECT

CARE4DIABETES (C4D): Reducing the burden of non-communicable diseases by providing a multidisciplinary lifestyle treatment intervention for type 2 diabetes

The overarching objective of the CARE4DIABETES Joint Action is to improve and foster health in the EU Member States by reducing the burden of type 2 diabetes and related risk factors, both at societal and personal level, through effective lifestyle treatment and training programmes.

The expected outcomes are to increase patients' well-being and quality of life, reduce healthcare associated costs, and promote capacity building of health systems towards more innovative and integrated type 2 diabetes interventions based on lifestyle changes.

The focus will be on tangible transnational activities with a potential to trigger diabetes related policies in Member States with the prospective to improve health and socio-economic outcomes.

The Joint Action project will be aimed at transferring the identified best practice and implementable research results

<https://c4djointaction.eu/about/> States' contexts.

PROJECT SUMMARY

The main objective of the CARE4DIABETES Joint Action (JA) is to improve and foster health in the EU Member States by reducing the burden of type 2 diabetes and related risk factors, both at societal and personal level, through effective lifestyle treatment programmes of patients.

The expected outcomes are to increase patients' health and quality of life, reduce healthcare associated costs, and promote capacity building of health systems towards more innovative and integrated type 2 diabetes interventions based on patients' lifestyle changes.

The Joint Action will be aimed at transferring and implementing an identified best practice across 12 Member States. The best practice is an evidence-based, reimbursed Dutch lifestyle treatment programme for type 2 diabetes, named **Reverse Diabetes2 Now** and developed by the NGO **Voeding Leeft** in the Netherlands. Its rationale lies in the promotion of lifestyle changes that can bring improved quality of life in people with type 2 diabetes and healthier blood glucose levels with potential lower medication consumption.

The Joint Action pilot actions will be implemented, monitored, and evaluated in **12 Member States** by involving approx. **860 patients** and up to **120 healthcare professionals**. Building on the outcomes of the pilot actions' experiences, the Joint Action partners will focus on sustainability for the long-term transfer of the best practice in their countries.

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BACKGROUND

Non-communicable diseases (NCDs), such as type 2 diabetes, represent major causes of disability, ill-health, health-related retirement, and premature death in the European Union (EU) and cause a considerable social and economic impact. To strengthen strategies for the treatment of diabetes and to further enhance sharing best practice among Member States, the EU4H Programme established a **Joint Action** grant under the thematic area of diabetes.

The Joint Action has a strong policy relevance as it has the potential to support Member States to promote the implementation of new evidence-based policies and actions on patients' empowerment, health promotion in patients with type 2 diabetes and cost-effective management of the disease, while improving the efficiency of health investments.

The Joint Action relevance to the call and to EU & international priorities is that it will foster innovative practices that:

- a) have the potential to reduce the health burden of type 2 diabetes by increasing the quality of life and extending life expectancy and
- b) decrease the cost of usual type 2 diabetes management including medications and/or improve the outcomes for a given investment.

The Joint Action will build up and contribute to frame EU policies and innovative approaches for NCDs like type 2

RELEVANCE

CARE4DIABETES will aim to reduce type 2 diabetes burden, as well as raise awareness and acceptance on improved and more innovative related lifestyle interventions, in line with EU policy framework and the Action Plan for Prevention and Control of NCDs in the WHO EU Region 2016-2027.

The Joint Action has a strong policy relevance as it has the potential to support member states to promote the implementation of new evidence-based policies and actions on patients' empowerment, health promotion in patients with type 2 diabetes and cost-effective management of the disease, while improving the efficiency of health investments.

The Joint Action relevance to the call and to EU & international priorities is that it will foster innovative practices that:

- a) have the potential to reduce the health burden of type 2 diabetes by increasing the quality of life and extending life expectancy and
- b) decrease the cost of usual type 2 diabetes management including medications and/or improve the outcomes for a given investment.

The relatively safe environment and the limited scope of the **pilot actions** will minimise the risks of implementing the innovative approach for type 2 diabetes reversal and facilitate the detailed analysis of the factors involved in its suc-

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ABOUT

PARTNERS

WORK PACKAGES

DELIVERABLES

NEWS

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CONTACT US

METHODOLOGY

The JA will combine the transfer and implementation of the selected best practice with the support given to Competent Authorities, policy makers, and other relevant organisations for the long-term sustainability of CARE4DIABETES pilot interventions.

The first step in this process will be identifying and assessing the transferability of a best practice intervention, which represent key preliminary steps to the implementation process.

Once an intervention has been identified as best practice and appropriate for transfer, the following step is to implement it in a new target setting. Laying out a formal implementation process is crucial given successful public health interventions rely on coordinated interactions between many people, tools, and processes. Finally, intervention monitoring and evaluations will be key to understand whether it is successful and should therefore be continued and scaled-up, or if the intervention needs to be amended or even cancelled.

To achieve successful practice implementation, the project methodology is built around 3 core interconnected milestones, which are reflected in the planned Work Packages (WPs):

1. Knowledge framework, stakeholders' engagement, and intervention's preparation (WP5)
2. CARE4DIABETES transfer to countries: Phase I (WP6) and Phase II implementation (WP7)
3. Evaluation and sustainability (WP3 and WP4)

“Partners” section

ABOUT

PARTNERS

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COORDINATORS

ES CONSEJERIA DE SALUD – PRINCIPADO DE ASTURIAS (CSPA)

ES SERVICIO DE SALUD DEL PRINCIPADO DE ASTURIAS (SESPA)

ES FUNDACIÓN PARA EL FOMENTO EN ASTURIAS DE LA INVESTIGACIÓN CIENTÍFICA APLICADA Y TECNOLOGÍA (FICYT)

PARTNERS

BE SCIENSANO (SCIENSANO)

BG MINISTERSTVO NA ZDRAVEOPAZVANETO (MoH BG)

BG REGIONAL HEALTH INSPECTORATE BLAGOEVGRAD (RHI)

FI TERVEYDEN JA HYVINVOINNIN LAITOS (THL)

EL 1ST YGEIONOMIKI PERIFEREA DYPE ATTIKIS (1st YPE ATTICA)

HU NEMZETI NEPEGESZSEGUGYI KOZPONT (NPHC)

IT ISTITUTO SUPERIORE DI SANITA (ISS)

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“Work Packages”

The screenshot shows the website page for WP1 Project Management and Coordination. The page includes a navigation menu with 'WORK PACKAGES' selected. A sidebar lists the work packages: WP1 Project management and coordination, WP2 Communication and dissemination, WP3 Evaluation, WP4 Sustainability, WP5 Preparatory actions, WP6 Phase I implementation (capacity building oriented), and WP7 Phase II implementation (after-care oriented). The main content area for WP1 states: 'This WP focuses on achieving a smooth management and quality assurance of CARE4DIABETES project. Objectives of this WP are: To manage the project and ensure results are reached. To guarantee a continuous exchange of information among partners and with the EC. To organise meetings appropriately. To supervise data management and ethical issues stemming from project activities.' A photo of people in a meeting is shown with the caption 'Foto de Jason Goodman en Unsplash'. The footer contains links for PROJECT INFORMATION, COORDINATOR (Consejería de Salud del Gobierno del Principado de Asturias), FINANCIAL COORDINATOR (FICYT - Foundation for the Promotion in Asturias of Applied Scientific Research), and DISCLAIMER (Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author).

§

The screenshot shows the website page for WP2 Communication and Dissemination. The page includes a navigation menu with 'WORK PACKAGES' selected. The main content area for WP2 states: 'The dissemination and communication activities of this WP aim to increase the visibility and impact of the CARE4DIABETES project and its implementation at national and European level. The dissemination activities will aim at sharing and promoting the progress and achievements of the project, it will also facilitate the participation of relevant stakeholders. Objectives of this WP are: To ensure results and deliverables of the JA are known by the general public. To actively engage stakeholders in the project. To define dissemination strategy and related key performance indicators. To implement a wide range of media and non-media communication. To ensure dissemination and to evaluate the impact. To favour the knowledge of the CARE4DIABETES pilot actions' experiences, and other relevant results in the EU and beyond.' A photo of glowing spheres is shown on the right side of the page.

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WP3 EVALUATION

This WP will monitor and evaluate performance of the Work Plan continuously, particularly the transfer progress and implementation of the pilot actions. As part of the work developed in this WP, impact indicators and a methodological framework will be developed.

Objectives of this WP are:

- To monitor and evaluate the project activities across all WPs, collect information, and ensure actions are conducted as planned.
- To develop and implement relevant impact indicators and a methodological framework, in order to oversee and evaluate impartially the progress made.
- To collect information on whether the project activities (including PDSA) are conducted as planned

WP4 SUSTAINABILITY

This WP aims at achieving a long-term project results impact, along with extended continuation of the pilot actions. General principles based on previous best practice experience will be identified.

Objectives of this WP are:

- To identify general principles of sustainable implementation, based on the analysis of the best practice experience.
- To define the essential elements of the process of transferability adaptation to facilitate the long-term sustainability of the pilot actions.
- To develop the methodology for country scale-up plans.
- Support development of recommendations at EU level

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WP5 PREPARATORY ACTIONS

This WP will gather information on best practices and preparation of local pilot actions. A plan for the best practice's implementation will be outlined. As part of this plan, an online community platform will be created.

Objectives of this WP are:

- To perform all preparatory actions for the best practice's implementation.
- To have a thorough understanding of the best practice features.
- To establish a detailed plan for transferring in each relevant Member State.
- To prepare the online community platform to complement patients' lifestyle training sessions on WP6 to produce an overall framework and guiding material for patients' recruitment

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Comissió de Salut del Govern de Catalunya FICVT - Fundación for the Promotion Views and opinions are

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WP6 PHASE I IMPLEMENTATION (CAPACITY BUILDING ORIENTED)

This WP focuses on the implementation of a 6-month Intensive Care Programme with patients and to monitor, collect, and to evaluate results applying two PDSA cycles.

Objectives of this WP are:

- To implement the Phase I capacity building oriented part of the best practice applying a Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) framework.
- To transfer, adapt, and translate materials for patients' lifestyle treatment.
- To train the healthcare professionals in charge of local pilot actions.
- To conduct the first intensive care phase of the intervention in the 12 countries including two PDSA cycles.
- To continuously monitor and evaluate the progress and interim results to correct potential bottlenecks.

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← → ↻ c4djointaction.eu/wp7-phase-ii-implementation-after-care-oriented/

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WP7 PHASE II IMPLEMENTATION (AFTER-CARE ORIENTED)

During this WP the Phase II (After Care Programme) will be implemented, with one PDSA cycle, tracking patients' evolution and performing periodic clinical checks. Data will be collected for final evaluation and preparation of sustainability conclusions.

Objectives of this WP are:

- To prepare and execute the Phase II after-care implementation, with the two patients' intervention group and including one PDSA cycle.
- To perform a close follow-up on patients after the intensive training programme of WP6.
- To implement dedicated after-care activities including continuous tracking and support of enrolled patients.
- To develop a health and socio-economic impact assessment about how transfer and implementation of the best practice was done.

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“Deliverables”

← → ↻ c4djointaction.eu/deliverables/

Care4Diabetes4JointAction > Deliverables

DELIVERABLES

WP1 Project management and coordination

- D1.1 – Management & Coordination plan
- D1.2 – FAIR Data Management Plan

WP2 Communication and dissemination

- D2.1 – Dissemination strategy
- D2.2 – Project website
- D2.3 – Dissemination & communication outcomes report

WP3 Evaluation

- D3.1 – Monitoring and Evaluation Plan
- D3.2 – Interim impact evaluation report
- D3.3 – Final impact evaluation report

WP4...

Foto de Kaleidico en Unsplash

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“News” section

Category Archives: News

First meeting of the CARE4DIABETES Spain consortium
27 Feb, 2023 By supervisor News
The Spanish Health Authorities have organized the first meeting to start with the execution of the European project CARE4DIABETES. A representative of the Spanish Ministry of Health has attended the meeting ...
[Read More >](#) 0 Comments

KICK-OFF MEETING CARE4DIABETES
13 Feb, 2023 By supervisor News
Date: 16-17 February 2023 Location: Oviedo (Asturias) / Face-to-face and Online
[Read More >](#) 0 Comments

Care4Diabetes in The Netherlands
2 Feb, 2023 By supervisor News
Asturias coordinates the European project Care4 Diabetes that validates good practices in the European Union to improve the quality of life of patients with type 2 diabetes through self-care. Professionals from the ...
[Read More >](#) 0 Comments

“Events” section

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16 FEB 2023 **Featured** February 16 - February 17
KICK-OFF MEETING
Palacio de los Condes de Toreno Plaza de Portier,9, Oviedo
vicenmiranda from Oviedo, España - 8. Real Instituto de Estudios Asturianos

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“Contact us” section

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CONTACT US

Contact Form

Your Name (required)

Your Email (required)

Subject

Your message

“EU funding visibility” section

← → ↻ c4djointaction.eu/contact-us-2/

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Parque de El Truebano
Instalaciones Deportivas El Cristo
Escuela Oficial
Filipo Pegatina / Clic Bar
Me Apto Food&Drinks
TEDI Comercio S.L.U
C. González Besada

PROJECT INFORMATION

C4D CARE 4 DIABETES Joint Action

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This website is part of the project CARE4DIABETES (C4D): The project CARE4DIABETES has received funding from the European Commission under GA 101082427

COORDINATOR

Consejería de Salud del Gobierno del Principado de Asturias

Ms. Marta Pisano González,
Calle Ciriaco Miguel Vigil, 9,
33005 Oviedo, Asturias, Spain
www.astursalud.es/astursalud
dgcuidados@asturias.org
T. +34 985105500 Ext: 17485

FINANCIAL COORDINATOR

FICYT – Foundation for the Promotion in Asturias of Applied Scientific Research and Technology

Calle Cabo Noval, 11,
33007 Oviedo, Asturias, Spain
web@c4djointaction.eu
T. +34 985207434

DISCLAIMER

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“Social networks links”

TARGET AUDIENCE

The information provided by the website will be addressed to the European Commission, the partners and affiliated entities of the project, other National and Regional health authorities from the EU Member States and beyond, all stakeholders identified in Task 2.1, Communication and Dissemination Strategy, as relevant for the project, health professionals, citizens suffering from Diabetes type 2, and the general public.

3. RESULTS

The main result is that **the website has been elaborated at month 1 of the project**. It was an achievement to have it ready on the date of the kick-off meeting to increase the impact and awareness of the project.

The logo was elaborated and finished during the first week of the project.

The social networks were created and finished during the second week of the project.

Management of the website and the social networks: a procedure for the management of the website and social networks has been elaborated and implemented during the second month of the project:

- The audience and potential recipients of the information to be shared have been identified, in collaboration with task 2.1-Communication and Dissemination Strategy.
- **Guidelines** or posting news on the website and social networks have been developed to share with project partners and affiliated entities so that they know how to send information to FICYT to feed the website and social networks (see Annex II)

- A **monitoring procedure** has been elaborated, in collaboration with WP2 leaders, to collect the information related to communication and dissemination activities carried out by the partners. The tool for the collection of information will be updated every six months and the information will be uploaded to Sygma (Participant Portal of EU) to comply with the periodic reporting obligations (see Annex III).
- The Task 2.2 leader will check the website weekly to find and fix bugs, mistakes and any other technical issue that may arise. Regarding the website new contents, FICYT will also assure that there is at least **one new post per month on the website and one per week on the Social Networks**. The Dissemination WP team will also carefully check and review each item to be published assuring the highest quality standards.

The website has recently been developed, so no results have been measured yet to monitor the scope of the information disseminated throughout the website and the social networks. Indicators of performance will be defined and measured in the framework of the dissemination and communication strategy of the project.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The conclusions got after the elaboration of this deliverable are summarized as follows considering the strengths and weaknesses of the results and including recommendations to be considered by other developers and coordinators of European projects.

STRENGTHS:

- The development of the website and the social networks at month 1 of the project which allows the consortium to have a tool for the presentation of the project to the National and regional Governments and other stakeholders. That is related to the final implementation of the project at National or regional level and its sustainability beyond its official duration.
- The elaboration of specific materials for dissemination and communication activities that are planned to be carried out during the project execution.

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- The development of guidelines and a monitoring tool for the dissemination and communication activities that will help verify if the dissemination and communication strategy is correct and will contribute to increase the impact of the project.

WEAKNESSES:

- The website and the social networks have been developed before the elaboration of the dissemination and communication strategy. That may lead to some difficulties to make decisions on the content and some delay in getting content to be disseminated.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

- The website and the social networks should be elaborated at the beginning of the project in order to start disseminating the activities of the project as soon as possible.
- The visual identity of the logo should be developed prior to the website and the social networks to allow the audience to quickly identify the dissemination activities and materials of the project.
- As many features of the visual identity of the project as possible should be used in other materials elaborated in the framework of the project.
- The logo of the project and the logo of the EU funding visibility should be included in all the materials and tools elaborated for the dissemination and communication activities of the European projects.
- Develop the dissemination and communication strategy of the project in parallel to the development of the webpage and social networks to allow that all the dissemination and communication activities planned for the project are addressed to the right audience and the most suitable channels are used for each specific activity. This will impact significantly on the awareness of the project.

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5. ANNEXES:

- ANNEX I: LOGO BASIC MANUAL

- ANNEX II: GUIDELINES FOR THE PUBLICATION OF NEWS ON THE WEBSITE AND SOCIAL NETWORKS

- ANNEX III: MONITORING PROCEDURE TOOL

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ANNEX 1

LOGO BASIC MANUAL

MANUAL BÁSICO

C4D

CARE **4** DIABETES

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Marca al agua

Opacidad 20%

Opacidad 15%

Versiones sin lema

Tintas planas

Pantone
Blue 072

Pantone
485

Cuatricromía

100% cian
95% magenta
0% amarillo
3% negro

0% cian
96% magenta
100% amarillo
0% negro

RGB

16 Red
6 Green
154 Blue

255 Red
10 Green
0 Blue

HEX/HTML

#10069F

#FF0A00

RAL

5002

2002

Partes de la marca

MARCA O
IMAGOTIPO

LOGOTIPO

IDENTIFICADOR

LEMA

MUSEO SANS ROUNDED

Museo Sans Rounded 300

a b c d e f g h i j k m n ñ
o p q r s t u v w x y z
A B C D E F G H I J K M N Ñ
O P Q R S T U V W X Y Z
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 0

Museo Sans Rounded 500

a b c d e f g h i j k m n ñ
o p q r s t u v w x y z
A B C D E F G H I J K M N Ñ
O P Q R S T U V W X Y Z
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 0

Museo Sans Rounded 900

**a b c d e f g h i j k m n ñ
o p q r s t u v w x y z
A B C D E F G H I J K M N Ñ
O P Q R S T U V W X Y Z
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 0**

Museo Sans Rounded 1000

**a b c d e f g h i j k m n ñ
o p q r s t u v w x y z
A B C D E F G H I J K M N Ñ
O P Q R S T U V W X Y Z
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 0**

Snickles

*a b c d e f g h i j k m n
o p q r s t u v w x y z
A B C D E F G H I J K M N
O P Q R S T U V W X Y Z
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 0*

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ANNEX II

GUIDELINES FOR THE PUBLICATION OF NEWS ON THE WEBSITE AND SOCIAL NETWORKS

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GUIDELINES FOR THE PUBLICATION OF NEWS ON THE WEBSITE AND SOCIAL NETWORKS

This document is a brief guide for CARE4DIABETES partners and affiliated entities to know how to transmit to the person responsible for the news items on the website and social networks, the information that can be published.

Each partner responsible for the content of a news item will be in charge of sending the content described in the following sections to the address antonio@ficyt.es

Ficyt will be responsible for adapting the information sent to the most appropriate language according to the dissemination channel used.

WEB NEWS

- 1. Title.** No limit to the number of characters, but preferably concise.
 - 2. Entry.** Summarises the text of the news item. This is the initial paragraph that summarises the most important data. It is the part of the text that appears when the news item is minimised. It should be brief, between 30 and 50 words).
 - 3. Keywords.** Suggestion: here we can establish the type of news: success story, funding, partner initiative, dissemination; and then add other keywords that can also function as hashtags: innovation, health, emotional wellbeing, food...)
 - 4. Body.** Body of the news item This is the development of the news item that has been summarised in the entry, in which the information is provided, and some topics related to it or information that is considered relevant are included. For the web there is no limit to the number of characters, although the tendency is for texts to be shorter and for news to be more visual.
 - 5. Image.** It is preferable that news items include images. You can send your own images, figures, etc. or indicate your preferences of themes to search in free image databases. THIS FIELD IS NOT COMPULSORY BUT RECOMMENDABLE.
- Important: Images must be your own or free. Always indicate the source when attaching an image to avoid copyright infringement.**
- 6. Caption.** If an image is sent, it is preferable to send the data to include the caption.
 - 7. Links.** At the bottom of the news item, you can include sources to expand the information, ideally include source, link and date on which it was available. THIS FIELD IS NOT COMPULSORY.

Once posted on the website, it will also be published on social networks.

NEWS ON SOCIAL NETWORKS

Twitter:

- 1. Text:** up to 280 characters + image. The summary of the 280 characters usually includes a mention of the entities involved.
- 2. Name and website of the entities/projects mentioned in the news item:** If the name of the entity is not known on Twitter, it is important that we have the name and/or website of the entity/project so that we can search for it and mention it to facilitate engagement.
- 3. Image:** the same as in the news item.
- 4. Hashtag:** it is included among the characters, it may not be added in the publication although it is the way to appear in searches, we would try to link it with the keywords included in the news item.
- 5. Link:** link to the news published on the website would be included to attract visitors to the project website.

LinkedIn:

- 1. Body:** There is no character limitation, but the texts should not be too long. For example, the entry in the news item can be published, but mentioning the entities or projects involved.
- 2. Name and website of the entities/projects mentioned:** to search the social network and mention them.
- 3. Image:** same as the news item.
- 4. Hashtag:** as there is no character limitation, it is advisable to include it. We will try to relate them to the key words of the news item.
- 5. Link:** a link to the news item published on the website would be included to attract visitors to the project website.

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WEBSITE NEWS TEMPLATE:

Title (compulsory)

Entry (compulsory)

Keywords (compulsory)

Include type of news item: funding, partner, success story, meeting

Body/News Content (compulsory)

Projects/ Entities implied (not compulsory)

Paste your image here (not compulsory but recommendable)

Description of the picture caption or subject

Indicate source (own, free,..):

Links: not compulsory

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TWITTER TEMPLATE:

280-character text

Name of entity/project or website involved

Hashtag: Preferably those of the web news will be used.

Image: Preferably those of the web news item will be used.

Link: Link to the web news

LINKEDIN TEMPLATE:

Text: Preferably the entry from the web news item.

Name of entity/project or website involved

Hashtag: Preferably those of the web news will be used.

Image: Preferably those of the web news item will be used.

Link: Link to the news item

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ANNEX III

MONITORING PROCEDURE TOOL

Publications

Control number	Type of Publisher Identification (PID) repository	PID of deposited publication	PID (publisher version of record)	Type of publication	Link to publication
P.01					
P.02					
P.03					
P.04					
P.05					

Title of the scientific publication	Authors	Title of the Journal or equivalent